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An assessment of a coastal altimetry data product in the Indonesian Waters

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Abstract. We analyzed the percentage of valid coastal altimetry Jason-2 X-TRACK-SLA data by Center for Topographic Studies in Sea and Hydrosphere (CTOH) and the waveforms from the Sensor Geophysical Data Record (SDGR) that are distributed by NOAA National Ocean Data Center around the Indonesian waters. In general, the percentage of valid data after the first point of the shoreline is greater than 90%. The percentage of valid data in steeper waters (86%) is higher than sloping waters (34%). The waveform types formed in coastal waters are peaky and Brown. However, spatially there is a difference where in a steep coast at a distance of > 5 km from the coastline the type of waveform is identified Brown, while on the sloping coast the brown type is found at a distance > 10 km. The SLA time series indicate seasonal variations in which the SLA is negative during the Southeast Monsoon (May-October) and positive during Northwest Monsoon (November-April).

1. Introduction

Indonesia is an archipelagic nation consisting of nearly 14,000 islands with a total coastline length exceeding 90 thousand kilometers. The Indonesian coastal and deep seas area highly dynamic environment with many physical processes, such as Indonesian Throughflow [1], equatorial origin Rossby and Kelvin waves [2;3], seasonal upwelling [4;5], sea level rise (SLR) and their variability [6]. Altimetry satellite data can be used for this related study; however, as it has been mentioned before, monitoring coastal waters circulation with altimetry is still a challenging issue because of the numerous constraints [7].

Global SLR is one of the impacts of global climate change and causes inundation of many small islands and coastal area in Indonesia. The scientific research indicates that global sea levels have been rising at a rate of 3.5 millimeters per year since the early 1990s, and the rate of increase varies considerably in different locations. As sea level is expected to rise further in the future (0.5 to 1 meter by 2100 and possibly more) [8]. The Sea level rise trend in South East Asia Seas including Indonesia

seas has increased by 38 mm per year [6]. SLR may contribute to a loss of arable land through inundation, affecting crop growth and yield [9]. Since brackish water fish pond and rice fields in Indonesia are mostly located in coastal zones, it is estimated that by year 2050 the area of paddy rice fields could be reduced by 182,556 ha in Java and Bali, 78,701 ha in Sulawesi, 25,372 ha in Kalimantan, 3,170 ha in Sumatra, and 2,123 ha in Lombok [10]. In South Kalimantan, tidal swamps have been reclaimed for various agricultural activities. This changing can be used to reduce coastal vulnerability due to SLR [11]. Therefore, monitoring of SLR and their impact on coastal area is very important to study in the Indonesian coastal waters.

Traditionally, sea level change has been estimated from tide gauge measurements, collected over the last century. Recently, approximately 100 units of tide gauges were installed in the Indonesia waters. This amount is certainly not adequate to cover the length of the Indonesian coastline of about 90,000 km. Thus, it is really required to have sea level information that is complete and accurate both spatially and temporally to collect data of sea level. To monitor the dynamics of sea level along the coastlines will be needed more than 400 units of tide gauges. The satellite altimeter data can be used as a complementary tool for covering the lack of sea-level data from tide gauge in Indonesian coastal waters [12].

Sea level measurement by satellite altimetry has been done since the early 1990s: ERS-1, Topex/Poseidon, ERS-2 GFO Jason-1 and ENVISAT, Jason-2, etc. [13, 14]. Radar altimetry has been developed to monitor the sea level with high accuracy [15, 16]. However, despite the many satellite instruments showing some ability to measure sea level, it is still hard to provide accurate altimeter-derived-measurement of sea level in the coastal area.

Most altimetry datasets are designed for the deep oceans because land contaminates the return signal of the altimeter. To resolve these issues, there was an effort in the last decade to improve the processing using a set of techniques (e.g., re-tracking, new corrections). One example is the coastal datasets that were corrected regionally through the use of X-TRACK, which is developed by Center for Topographic Studies in the Sea and Hydrosphere (CTOH). Before utilizing the dataset widely, it is necessary to assess the potential of this CTOH data, especially in the Indonesian coastal waters. This study attempts to analyze the potential altimetry Jason-2 data along the coast of Indonesian waters.

2. Methods

2.1. Coastal Altimetry Data

In this study we used the along-track (X-TRACK) satellite altimeter data product, developed by CTOH (<http://ctoh.legos.obs-mip.fr/products/coastal-products/>), and Sensor Geophysical Data Record (SDGR) that are distributed by NOAA National Ocean Data Center (https://podaac.jpl.nasa.gov/dataset/OSTM_L2_SGDR_D).

SLA projected onto reference tracks with a spatial interval of about 6-7 km between points (1 second) are computed using the X-TRACK software [7], developed at LEGOS France. The CTOH computes regional along-track sea level anomaly (SLA) products for altimeter Jason-2 missions from 2008-2013. We used Jason-2 data along-track (1 Hz) of Indonesian coastal tracks (figure 1). Sea level data were derived from level 2 of GRD in NetCDF format.

Figure 1. Jason-2 satellite altimetry of track of 2008-2013 in Indonesian waters. The red lines are ascending pass and black lines are descending pas.

2.2. Sea Surface Height (SSH) measurement

Satellite observations of sea surface height are available along the ground-tracks of Jason-2 satellite altimetry missions. Measurement of SSH was performed with various corrections in order to obtain actual distances between a satellite and sea level, as the following [17]:

$$R_{cor} = R_{obs} - \Delta R_{dry} - \Delta R_{wet} - \Delta R_{iono} - \Delta R_{ssb} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

where (R_{cor}) is the corrected range, (R_{obs}) = $c t/2$ is the computed range from travel time t observed and c is the speed of the radar pulse neglecting refraction.

Altimeters measure the distance between the sea surface and the satellite. The height, h , of the sea surface above references ellipsoid is given as:

$$h = H - R_{cor} = H - (R_{obs} - \Delta R_{dry} - \Delta R_{wet} - \Delta R_{iono} - \Delta R_{ssb}) \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

where H is the height of the spacecraft determined through orbit determination. Atmospheric disturbances are corrected, among others: the effects of the ionosphere (Δh_{iono}), wet troposphere (Δh_{wet}), dry troposphere (Δh_{dry}), the bias condition of the sea (Δh_{ssb}), tidal correction value (h_{tides}), and dynamic atmospheric corrected value (h_{atm}).

The actual sea surface height is a superposition of these geophysical signals and the dynamic sea surface height, h_D such that [10]:

$$SSH(h) = h_D + h_{geoid} + h_{tides} + h_{atm} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

The sea surface high anomaly (h_{sla}) determined as:

$$h_{sla} = H - R_{obs} - \Delta h_{dry} - \Delta h_{wet} - \Delta h_{iono} - \Delta h_{ssb} - h_{tides} - h_{atm} - h_{MSS} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

2.3. Data processing and analysis

The altimeter satellites were originally designed to observe offshore waters so that the raw data produced around the coast was very limited in both quality and quantity. Therefore, various studies have been conducted to improve the quality and quantity of altimeter data around the coast. One of

them is the Altimeter-Based Investigations in Corsica, Capraia and Contiguous Areas (ALBICOCCA) research project in the Northwest Mediterranean Sea. Through this project developed Additional developments lead to the X-TRAC tool. With this tool, new classical GDR processing is done to produce coastal altimeter data [19].

The approach is to use more detailed models for responding to the high frequency of tidal and atmospheric responses, reducing satellite orbit errors and increasing mean sea surface resolution. The application of x-track tool is expected to improve the quality of altimeter products i.e.: SSH, MSSH, SLA in coastal areas [19]. A more complete explanation of data processing and analysis can be found in the User Handbook of CTOH Along-Track Sea Level Anomalies regional products (X-TRACK).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Potential coastal altimeter data

Figure 2 shows the percentage of along-track available valid data from the Jason-2 missions 2008 - 2013 period in Indonesian coastal waters and adjacent seas. The along-track valid data indicate that the availability are greater than 90%, except one near shore points from the coastal line. The average percentage of valid data on the first footprint from the coastline in shallow water such as the Java Sea (34%) is lower than the coastal in the deep sea (86%) such as the eastern Indian Ocean (figure 2b).

Generally, the percentage of data availability of the X-TRACK-SLA product after the first point from the coastline is greater than 90%. However, the percentage of valid data in deep waters is higher than in coastal waters (figure 2c). The results of this study are consistent with those shown in the Northwestern Mediterranean Sea, the X-TRACK-SLA data significantly increase the number of valid data [18]. The altimeter satellite data around the coast is usually low quality due to land contamination of the satellite footprints, the high frequency ocean response to tidal and atmospheric loading [19].

3.2. Types of waveform

The radar altimeter waveforms provide the range between the satellite and the surface at nadir via two-way travel time of the transmitted pulse, the Significant Wave Height (SWH) via the slope of the waveform leading edge, and the backscattering coefficients which represent the surface roughness and characteristics via the returned power [20]. Figure 3 shows the Jason-2 track 246 waveforms at a distance of 0-5 km, 5-10, and 50-100 km from the southern coast of Java Island.

Figure 2. Top: (a) percentage of data availability for along-tracks data from the Jason-2 missions. Bottom: (b) the blue circles highlight region where the percentage of availability data in coastal shallow waters and the red circles highlight region the coastal deep waters, and (c) Comparison of the percentage of valid data in shallow water coastal (the Java Sea) and deep coastal waters (the eastern Indian Ocean off Southern Java) calculated from the first point up to 100 km from coast line.

The waveform formed near the coast (0-5 km) on track 246 is a peaky type (figure 3a) and more than 10 km is Brown type. Waveform near the coast is strongly influenced by the noise generated by terrestrial and shallow waters [19]. The ideal waveform is the Brown waveform generally formed in the open seas far away from the main land. An average 94% Brown waveform type can be found at a distance of more than 15 km from the shore [21]. However Waveform in the southern coast of Java island at a distance of 5-10 km from the coast is a Brown type (figure 4b). Meanwhile the waveform types in the same distance in the north coast of Java island is peaky (figure 4a) [22], where the depth is shallow with an average depth of 30 meters [23].

Figure 3. Types of Waveform Jason-2 track 242 of cycle 104.

The bathymetry in southern coast of Java Island shows that the depth of coastal waters at a distance of 5 km and more from the coast > 500 m. The south coast of Java Island is also directly related to the Indian Ocean so that the water characteristics near the coast it is classified as an deep sea. The ideal Brown waveform type is generally formed in the high seas (figure 4b) [24]. The other factors that may affect signals received by satellite sensors and affect the waveforms are the depth and shape of the water surface, coastal environmental conditions, atmospheric aerosols, buildings (e.g., lighthouses or vessels), and others [25].

Figure 4. Types of waveform at a distance of 5-10 Km from the coast (a) North coast of Java Island (shallow waters) [21] and (b) South coast of Java Island (deep waters).

3.3. Mean Sea Surface Height (MSSH)

The MSSH is substantially obtained by averaging all valid SSHs at each point along track. It accounts for geoid and Mean Dynamic Topography (MDT). MSSH is estimated at each of the altimeter Jason-2 foot points. Generally, the MSSH increases from offshore to coast. The MSSH in Indonesian waters is shown in figure 5. The MSSH located at each foot points covers in the Indonesian water ununiformly. And it indicates well-known patterns, such as the MSSH is much higher in eastern Indonesia water (western Pacific) than that in eastern Indian Ocean off south Java.

The highest of MSSH is 80 cm occur in Eastern Indonesia waters off North Papua, and the lowest is -20 cm in Eastern Indian Ocean off Sumatera and Java. This sea-level difference leads to establish the Indonesian Throughflow from the Pacific to the Indian Ocean [24].

Figure 5. Mean Sea Surface Height [in cm] along the track of Jason-2 missions (2008-2013).

3.4. Sea-Level Anomaly (SLA)

Sea-level anomaly is the difference between the sea-level and the mean sea level for this time of year. For example, we analyzed the SLA time series on the Jason-2 track 064, and cycle-latitude plot (Hovmoller diagram) of SLA along selected track in the southern coast of Java Island (figure 6). The sea-level displays the number of months/cycles each year experiencing positive or negative anomalies. The SLA is negative during the Southeast Monsoon (SEM) period from June to October, meanwhile positive SLA occurs during the Northwest Monsoon (NWM) period from November to March. This seasonal change of SLA expresses a response of sea surface to reversal monsoon winds system. During the SEM period, the wind-driven Ekman transport in the southern coast of Java is toward offshore causing sea-level decreases. In contrary, during the NWM near the coastal area of southern Java Ekman transport toward the coast that pills up surface water near the coastal region.

The difference of sea-level between the SEM and NWM period in the southern of Java Island is approximately 80 cm. Generally during NWM period, monthly mean of sea-level height in Indonesian waters increases such as in south Java waters, Makassar Strait, and Banda Sea [5, 26-27]. The SLA changes in the southern coast of Java Island are strongly influenced by the monsoon winds in the Indonesian waters [28-29]. During the SEM period the easterly monsoon winds blow along southern coast of Java and produces Ekman transport toward offshore, which then generate coastal upwelling. This causes sea level to drop due to an offshore Ekman transport [4,5].

Figure 6. (a) Time series of SLA and (b) cycle-latitude plot (Hovmoller diagram) of SLA for all ground point along selected Jason-2 track 064 in the cost of southern Java Island.

4. Conclusion

The altimetry data of X-TRACK-SLA from CTOH product in Indonesian coastal waters showed that more than 90% of recorded SLA data are valid for 5 years of the Jason-2 missions. In general, the percentage of valid data in steeper coastal waters is higher than the sloping coastal waters. It shows that coastal altimetry data are potential to be used for coastal dynamics and sea level variability studies in the Indonesian coastal waters. The type of waveform formed in Indonesian coastal waters is a type of peaky and Brown type. The waveform type in Indonesian coastal waters is not only affected by distance from a coast but also influenced by water depth. The variability of SLA anomaly in Indonesian coastal waters exhibits large seasonal change that is influenced by monsoon winds system. Negative SLA occurs during the SEM period, while positive SLA is during the NWM period.

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